

Confirmation of the Tourism Marketing Mix Model in the Perspective of Foreign Tourists

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Abstract

This study aims to confirm the tourism marketing mix model in the perspective of foreign tourists. This study used 213 respondents from foreign tourists in Bali. The hypothesis of this study was tested using the Structural Equation Model (SEM). This research found : 1) Pull motivation (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), 2) Push motivation (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), 3) Destination image (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (Y2), 4) Pull motivation (X1) does not significantly influence tourist satisfaction (Y2), 5) Push motivation (X2) does not significantly influence the destination image (Y1), 6) Tourist satisfaction (Y2) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction loyalty tourists (Y2)

Keywords: Tourist, Pull Motivation, Push Motivation, Marketing Tourism, Destination Image

I. Introduction

Bali Island is the most popular tourist destination in Indonesia. The total number of foreign tourists visiting Indonesia through the entrance of Ngurah Rai Airport reached 40% as of October 2016, with the value of Bali's foreign exchange receipts for Indonesia from the tourism sector amounting to 70 Trillion Rupiah. With a total budget of 3 trillion Rupiah from the Ministry of Tourism to promote tourism in Indonesia 2016. There has been an increase in foreign tourist arrivals, especially to Bali, from 4,001,835 (January - December 2015) to 4,071,905 (January - October 2016).

Bali Culture Tourism is Bali tourism which is based on Balinese Culture which is imbued with the teachings of Hinduism and the philosophy of Tri Hita Karana as the main potential by using tourism as a vehicle for its actualization. That way, a dynamic reciprocal relationship between tourism and culture can be realized which makes them both develop synergistically, harmoniously and sustainably in order to provide prosperity to the community, cultural and environmental sustainability. Bali continues to implement culture-based tourism with local wisdom that breathes Hinduism, the development of tourism based on local wisdom by promoting the philosophy of "Tri Hita Karana" or three balance relations between humans and humans, humans and nature, humans and God.

The development of Bali Tourism from year to year is strongly influenced by cultural diversity factors that are owned by the Balinese people. The customs, arts and culture of Bali as the dominant basic potential in it implies an ideal of a reciprocal relationship between tourism and culture. Such Bali tourism has been going on for a long time, has been received and brought tourists from various regions in Indonesia, also from various countries in the world, regardless of religion and background.

Bashar & Ahmad (2010) have found tourist motivation is closely associated with destination's competitive advantage and image. As tourism is increasingly becoming an important sector in Jordan's economy, it can be argued that major findings of this study have significant policy and managerial implications for the country's core attractions and support services in tourism. These are fundamental in extending length of stay, increasing satisfaction and enhancing destination loyalty of foreign tourists. Future research may consider generating more precise applications related to destination behavior, especially concerning satisfaction and destination loyalty. Subsequent studies may also consider multiple dimensions in tourism motivation and integrate the approaches used by previous models.

Ian Phau, Sean Lee and Vanessa Quintal (2013) have found The results of a factor analysis revealed three push factors and three pull factors. Other analyses included an evaluation of the interrelationship between these factors in terms of different socio demographic subgroups and a general correlation analysis on the interrelationship among push and pull factors. This study provides useful managerial and practical implications for park managers, policymakers and communication strategists to gain an understanding of how push and pull factors affect tourists and their choice of private parks.

Rami F. Tawil & Ahmed M. Al Tamimi (2013) have found The main three push factors were (1) 'To travel to a country that I have not visited before', (2) 'To see something different that I don't normally see - something new and exciting', and (3) 'To experience cultures that are different from mine', while the main three pull factors included: (1) 'Safety and Security', (2) 'Weather', and (3) 'Cultural and historical places'. These were viewed as the most important push and pull factors influencing Chinese tourists to Jordan. By using cluster analysis, this study showed that it is possible to segment Chinese tourists to Jordan based on push and pull motivational factors. The three segments regarding push factors were labeled as 'Novelty & Knowledge seeking', 'Rest & relaxation' and 'Prestige & Ego-enhancement'. While the three segments regarding pull factors were labeled as 'Weather, Safety, and Cleanliness', 'Cultural & historical attractions' and 'Travel arrangements & Convenience'.

Mai Ngoc Khuong and Huynh Thi Thu Ha (2014) have found push and pull factors had directly positive influences on tourist's return intention to Vietnam. In addition, the results also showed that push and pull factors were indirectly affected tourist's return intention through their destination satisfaction. Consequently, business organizations working in the tourism sector should take into account the essential roles of push and pull factors, in order to attract more potential visitors, enhance their destination satisfaction and encourage them to re-visit Vietnam.

Nemanja Tomiš, et.al (2014) have found there are significant differences among several motivation factors when it comes to Danish and international students. The contribution of this study is its indication towards which factors influence city destination choice among young people which will further enable European cities to develop and promote more appropriate and satisfactory tourism products and services for their young visitors.

Reihanian, et.al (2015) have found visitors are pushed to the park for relaxing, and pulled by nature as a product. It was also clear that gender, marital status and province of the residence had not a significant influence on the push and pull factors. With the current number of other type of tourism competing for nature based tourism, this kind of information can imply that the management of national parks should not only focus on the identified travel motives, but also focus on other push and pull factors, in order to contribute to the sustainability of parks' development.

Erica E. Dolinting, et.al (2015) have found domestic sport tourists were more significantly motivated by intellectual, social, stimulus-avoidance and competence mastery motives than international sport tourists. With respect to the pull factors, result shows some difference in perceptions of destination image between domestic and international sport tourists.

Javid Seyidov & Roma Adomaitienė (2016) have found the age, monthly income and marital status of local Azerbaijani travellers affect their travel behaviour especially in the duration of their trip. Destination amenities, tourism infrastructure, environmental features, human resources and price are the important attributes for local tourists in choosing tourism destination.

Senutha P Ratthinan & Nor Hafizah Selamat (2017) have found indicate three distinct push and pull factors that impacts their motivation. The finding reinforces the increasing demand for travel among women students and the fact that technology has fundamentally reshaped the way travel is planned. This call for tourism stakeholders to make significant shift towards innovative initiatives that will be able to enhance the potential of the youth and student niche market.

Deša Karamehmedović (2018) has found the most important push factor is "education about culture, history, and the heritage of Dubrovnik" and the most important pull factor is the "City Walls".

The hypothesis of this study are 1) There is an influence of the push factors on the destination image in Bali, 2) There is an influence of the pull factor on the destination image in Bali, 3) There is an influence of the destination image on the satisfaction of foreign tourists in Bali, 4) There is an influence of the push factors on the satisfaction of foreign tourists in Bali, 5) There is an influence of pull factors on the satisfaction of foreign tourists in Bali, 6) There is an influence of satisfaction of foreign tourists on the loyalty of foreign tourists in Bali

II. Reset Methodology

Hypothesis testing using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Brannick (1995) in Kelloway (1995) suggested that covariance structure models can be used to test various complex models. Various tourist loyalty research models also use SEM as a model test tool, as in the research of Yoon and Uysal (2003), Chi (2005). SEM is a statistical model that

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explains the relationships among a number of variables, by examining the structure of the relationships among the variables that exist in the model.

The number of respondents was determined based on the ideal sample size of the SEM-AMOS structural model analysis tool, amounting to 213 respondents for the category of foreign tourists at each stage of the study.

Tabel 1 Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Man	123	57.7	57.7	57.7
	Woman	90	42.3	42.3	100.0
	Total	213	100.0	100.0	

III. Result & Discussion

In Table 1 it shows that the majority of respondents in this study were the majority of men totaling 123 people (57.7%) and women totaling 90 people (42.3%).

Tabel 2 Country of Origin

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Argentina	1	.5	.5	.5
	Australia	12	5.6	5.6	6.1
	Austria	1	.5	.5	6.6
	Belanda	40	18.8	18.8	25.4
	Belarusia	1	.5	.5	25.8
	Belgia	7	3.3	3.3	29.1
	Brazil	2	.9	.9	30.0
	Denmark	2	.9	.9	31.0
	Finlandia	3	1.4	1.4	32.4
	Hongkong	1	.5	.5	32.9
	Irlandia	3	1.4	1.4	34.3
	Italia	15	7.0	7.0	41.3
	Jerman	27	12.7	12.7	54.0
	Kanada	6	2.8	2.8	56.8
	Luxembourg	1	.5	.5	57.3
	Norwegia	2	.9	.9	58.2
	Perancis	17	8.0	8.0	66.2
	Portugal	1	.5	.5	66.7
	Rusia	9	4.2	4.2	70.9
	Selandia Baru	4	1.9	1.9	72.8
	Slovakia	1	.5	.5	73.2
	Slovenia	1	.5	.5	73.7
	Spanyol	5	2.3	2.3	76.1
	Swedia	8	3.8	3.8	79.8
	Swiss	13	6.1	6.1	85.9
	UK	8	3.8	3.8	89.7
	Ukraina	1	.5	.5	90.1
	USA	21	9.9	9.9	100.0
Total		213	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents in this study were the majority of foreign tourists from the Netherlands totaling 40 people (18.8%).

Tabel 3 Age Group

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Age 50 years or more	46	21.6	21.6	21.6
	Age less than 50 years	167	78.4	78.4	100.0
	Total	213	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents in this study were the majority of tourists who became respondents aged less than 50 years as many as 167 people (78.4%) and the remaining 46 people (21.6%) respondents were aged 50 years or more.

Tabel 4 Frequency of Tourist Visits

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Coming the 2nd time	43	20.2	20.2	20.2
	Come more than 2 times	105	49.3	49.3	69.5
	Come first time	65	30.5	30.5	100.0
	Total	213	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows that the majority of respondents in this study were the majority of tourists who came more than 2 times to Bali as many as 105 respondents (49.3%), while the first-time tourists were 65 respondents (30.5%) and tourists who came twice as many as 43 respondents (20.2%).

Validity Test

To test the validity with the C.F.A test or construct validity test is used to see whether the indicator is feasible to sustain latent variables. Indicators are said to be valid if the criteria ratio (CR) > 1.96 with a probability value (P) < 0.05 using the help of AMOS software. The results of the validity test can be seen in Table 5 as follows:

Table 5 Validity Test

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Y1	<---	X1	,956	,416	2,301	,021	
Y1	<---	X2	,209	,050	4,207	***	
Y2	<---	Y1	1,327	,241	5,502	***	
Y2	<---	X2	-,017	,056	-,308	,758	
Y2	<---	X1	-,639	,346	-1,845	,065	
Y3	<---	Y2	,631	,091	6,971	***	
X1.7	<---	X1	1,000				
X1.6	<---	X1	1,014	,507	2,002	,045	
X1.5	<---	X1	2,255	,917	2,458	,014	
X1.4	<---	X1	2,729	1,083	2,521	,012	
X1.3	<---	X1	2,627	1,039	2,528	,011	
X1.2	<---	X1	2,550	1,014	2,514	,012	
X1.1	<---	X1	2,468	,982	2,514	,012	
X2.15	<---	X2	1,000				
X2.14	<---	X2	,899	,102	8,816	***	
X2.13	<---	X2	1,025	,113	9,043	***	
X2.12	<---	X2	1,085	,116	9,328	***	
X2.11	<---	X2	1,005	,108	9,336	***	
X2.10	<---	X2	,718	,093	7,707	***	
X2.9	<---	X2	,557	,088	6,332	***	
X2.8	<---	X2	,962	,107	8,991	***	

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X2.7	<---	X2	,993	,108	9,204	***
X2.6	<---	X2	,421	,074	5,704	***
X2.5	<---	X2	,665	,093	7,134	***
X2.4	<---	X2	,788	,103	7,641	***
X2.3	<---	X2	,505	,083	6,057	***
X2.2	<---	X2	,488	,081	6,054	***
X2.1	<---	X2	,577	,086	6,738	***
Y1.1	<---	Y1	1,000			
Y1.2	<---	Y1	1,272	,244	5,221	***
Y1.3	<---	Y1	1,099	,191	5,750	***
Y1.4	<---	Y1	1,406	,229	6,146	***
Y1.5	<---	Y1	1,507	,240	6,270	***
Y1.6	<---	Y1	1,174	,228	5,154	***
Y1.7	<---	Y1	1,198	,210	5,704	***
Y2.1	<---	Y2	1,000			
Y2.2	<---	Y2	1,007	,089	11,320	***
Y2.3	<---	Y2	1,035	,091	11,386	***
Y2.4	<---	Y2	1,138	,098	11,628	***
Y3.1	<---	Y3	1,000			
Y3.2	<---	Y3	1,287	,147	8,777	***

In Table 6 it is found that all CR values > 1.96. Thus it can be concluded that all instruments namely Push factor (X1), Attractor Motivation (X2), Destination Image (Y1), Tourist Satisfaction (Y2), Tourist Loyalty (Y3) validity is fulfilled.

Reliability Test

Reliability test with the reliability construct test is used to see the consistency of the data. This means that if the > 0.6 then it is categorized that the indicators in the study are good. Following are the results of the reliability test in Table 7.

Table 7 Reliability Test

Indicator	Reliability Construct
Push Factor (X1)	0,713
Pull Factor (X2)	0,885
Destination Image (Y1)	0,794
Tourist Satisfaction (Y2)	0,874
Tourist Loyalty (Y3)	0,789

Picture 1. Structural Equation Model AMOS

Testing the goodness of fit model is carried out in seven stages, namely χ^2 (df), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness-fit index (AGFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), normalized fit index (NFI), comparative fit index (CFI), and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) with predetermined measurement value criteria.

Tabel 8. Goodness of Fit

Index	Criteria	Result	Model
	\leq , Chi square dari df is 555		
chi square	with sig level 5% = 0.000	1728,019	Good
GFI	> 0,05	0,675	Good
AGFI	> 0,90	0,630	Good
IFI	> 0,90	0,664	Not Good
TLI	> 0,90	0,635	Not Good
CFI	> 0,90	0,660	Not Good
NFI	> 0,90	0,574	Not Good
RMSEA	< 0,07	0,100	Not Good

Based on Table 8, it is found that some of the tests in the model feasibility test have met the specified criteria value. Obtained values on GFI, AGFI is greater than 0.90, while IFI, TLI, CFI, and NFI are less than 0.90 as shown in the table while the RMSEA value is still above 0.07.

Hypothesis testing is based on the results of structural model tests (inner models) which include parameter coefficients and t-statistics as follows:

1) Testing the Inner Model

The statistical hypothesis for the inner model is the exogenous latent variable to endogenous. This can be seen in the following table:

Table 9. Inner Weight Results on SPSS Output

F.Exogen/ F.Endogen	Direct Effect					
	Destination Image (Y1)		Tourist Satisfaction (Y2)		Tourist Loyalty (Y3)	
	Coef.	P.Value	Coef.	P.Value	Coef.	P.Value
Push Factor (X1)	0,956	0,021	-0,639	0,065		
Pull Factor (X2)	0,209	0,000	-0,017	0,758		
Destination Image (Y1)			1,327	0,000		
Tourist Satisfaction (Y2)					0,631	0,000

Based on Table 9 obtained:

- 1) Push factor (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H1 was accepted.
- 2) Pull factor (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H2 was received.
- 3) Destination image (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (Y2), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H3 was accepted.
- 4) Push factor (X1) does not significantly influence on tourist satisfaction (Y2), this is known from the p-value $> \alpha$, which is a p-value of 0.065 while α of 0.05. This shows that H4 was rejected.
- 5) Pull Factor (X2) does not significantly influence on tourist satisfaction (Y2), this is known from the p-value $> \alpha$, the p-value of 0,758 while α of 0.05. This shows that H5 was rejected.
- 6) Tourist satisfaction (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on tourist loyalty (Y2), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, that is, the p-value of 0.411 while α of 0.05. This shows that H6 was accepted.

3.1 Pull motivation (X1) has a positive and significant effect on destination image (Y1)

The results of the study show that pull motivation has a positive and significant effect on the image of the tourism destination of the Province of Bali, meaning that more tourists are motivated to travel to the Province of Bali, the image of the destination of the Province of Bali as a tourist area will continue to increase. The image of the tourist destination of the Province of Bali is very dependent on this motivational motivation, so it is necessary to try to encourage the population of Indonesia and the world population to come to the Province of Bali. One of the efforts that must be made is to make a more interesting promotion by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy by collaborating with tourism stakeholders in the Province of Bali to continue to foster motivational motivations in the Indonesian and world population to take a vacation to the Province of Bali as often as possible with longer stays. The results of this study are the same as the results of a study conducted by Dagustani, et.al (2018) finding pull motivation to have a positive and significant effect on destination imagery in the eco-tourism region of the South coast of West Java, and Haarhoff (2018) finding that pull motivation has a positive and significant effect on image of the destination at Kimberley Resort.

3.2 Push motivation (X2) has a positive and significant effect on destination image (Y1)

The results showed that the attractor's motivation had a positive and significant effect on the image of the tourism destination of the Province of Bali, meaning that the increasing motivation of the attractor would have an impact on the increasing image of the tourism destination of the Province of Bali. Tourism objects and attractions play an important role in raising the image of tourism destinations because tourists will look for something different from one tourist place to another so that it becomes a beautiful memory that is difficult to forget. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Haarhoff (2018) to find the pull of motivation to have a positive and significant effect on destination images at Kimberley Resort.

3.3 Destination image (Y1) has positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (Y2)

The results showed that the destination image has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in the Province of Bali, meaning that the increasing image of the tourism destination of the Province of Bali will have an impact on increasing tourist satisfaction in the Province of Bali. Tourists feel satisfaction due to a good destination image so that this can trigger word of the mouth. The results of this study are in line with the results of research from Bediova & Ryglova (2015) finding destination images have a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction at Ski Resorts Customers, Hanif, et.al (2016) finding destination images having a positive and significant effect on satisfaction of tourists visiting Kota Batu, dan Ermawati & Prihandono (2018) found the destination image had a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in Dieng Plateau, Wonosobo regency

3.4 Pull motivation (X1) does not have a significant positive effect on tourist satisfaction (Y2)

Pull motivation does not have a significant positive effect on tourist satisfaction in the Province of Bali, meaning that more and more tourists are motivated to make tourist visits, so there is no increase in tourist satisfaction in holidaying in the Province of Bali. The motivation of tourists is an important concern for tourism stakeholders which not only affects the image of the destination but also affects tourist satisfaction. The strategy of encouraging world tourists to go on holiday to Bali is a must to be considered and implemented through integrated government policies. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Kuong & Ha (2014) finding motivating drivers positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Ermawati & Prihandono (2018) found the motivation of drivers to have a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in Dieng Plateau, Wonosobo regency

3.5 Push motivation (X2) has a positive and significant effect on destination image (Y1)

Push motivation has a positive and significant impact on the image of tourism destinations in the Province of Bali, meaning that the increasing motivation of attractors has an impact on the image of the destination. The results of this study require stakeholders to improve the quality of tourist attraction so as to encourage the destination image to be even better in the Province of Bali. The results of this study are the same as the results of research from Kuong & Ha (2014) found that attractor motivation has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, Ermawati & Prihandono (2018) found that attracting motivation has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction in Dieng Plateau , Wonosobo regency

3.6 Tourist satisfaction (Y2) has a positive and significant effect on tourist loyalty (Y3)

Tourist satisfaction (Y2) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (Y3), meaning that the more tourist satisfaction increases, the more tourist loyalty (Y3) increases. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Hanif, et.al (2016) finding that tourist satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the loyalty of tourists visiting Kota Batu, Kuong & Ha (2014) finding that tourist satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on return intention / desire to return to Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam, Rajesh (2013) found that tourist satisfaction had a positive and significant effect on tourist loyalty

IV. Conclusions & Suggestions

The results of the Destination Development Model research in the Traveling Motivation Perspective can be summarized as follows.

- 1) Pull motivation (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H1 was accepted.
- 2) Push motivation (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the destination image (Y1), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H2 was received.
- 3) Destination image (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction (Y2), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H3 was accepted.
- 4) Pull motivation (X1) does not significantly influence tourist satisfaction (Y2), this is known from the p-value $> \alpha$, which is a p-value of 0.065 while α of 0.05. This shows that H4 was rejected.
- 5) Push motivation (X2) does not significantly influence the destination image (Y1), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, ie the p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H5 was accepted.
- 6) Tourist satisfaction (Y2) has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction loyalty tourists (Y2), this is known from the p-value $< \alpha$, which is a p-value of 0,000 while α of 0.05. This shows that H7 was accepted.

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The suggestions from the results of the research on the Destination Development Model in the Traveling Motivation Perspective are as follows.

- 1) Stakeholders in the tourism industry must continually improve tourism promotion to be able to attract Indonesian tourists and world tourists to holiday in Bali
- 2) Stakeholders in the tourism industry must continually improve objects and attractions to be able to improve the image of tourism destinations in the Province of Bali

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REFERENCES

- [1] Bediova Monika & Ryglova Katerina, The Main Factors Influencing The Destination Choice, Satisfaction And The Loyalty Of Ski Resorts Customers In The Context Of Different Research Approaches, Volume 63 Number 2, 2015, Acta Universitatis Agriculturae Et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis
- [2] Chi, G., *A Study of Developing Destination Loyalty Model*. Oklahoma: Oklahoma University, 2005
- [3] Dagustani Dani, Kartini Dwi, Oesman Yevis Marty, Kaltum Umi, Destination Image of Tourist: Effect of Travel Motivation and Memorable Tourism Experience, Volume 17 (2), 2018: 307 – 318, P-ISSN: 1412-8969; E-ISSN: 2461-0771, Etikonomi, 2018
- [4] Ermawati Feni & Pihandono Dorojatun, The Influence Of Destination Image, Push And Pull Travel Motivation Towards Tourist Loyalty Through Tourist Satisfaction, Management Analysis Journal 7 (4) (2018), 2018
- [5] Esichaikul, R., Travel motivations, behavior and requirements of European senior tourists to Thailand. *Sukhothai Journal of Thammathirat Open University*, 47-58., 2012
- [6] Haarhoff Rene, Tourist perceptions of factors influencing destination image: a case study of selected Kimberley resorts, Volume 7 (4) - (2018) ISSN: 2223-814X, African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure, 2018
- [7] Hanif Asya, Kusumawati Andriani, Mawardi M.Kholid, Pengaruh Citra Destinasi terhadap Kepuasan Wisatawan serta Dampaknya terhadap Loyalitas Wisatawan (Studi pada Wisatawan Nusantara yang berkunjung ke Kota Batu), Vol.38 No.1 September 2016, Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis, 2016
- [8] Khuong Mai Ngoc & Ha Huynh Thi Thu, The Influences of Push and Pull Factors on the International Leisure Tourists' Return Intention to Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam – A Mediation Analysis of Destination Satisfaction, Vol. 5, No. 6, December 2014, International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance, 2014
- [9] Pitana, I. G., *Sosiologi Pariwisata: Kajian Kepariwisata dalam Paradigma Intergratif menuju pariwisata spritual*. Yogyakarta: Andi, 2008
- [10] Rajesh R., Impact of Tourist Perceptions, Destination Image and Tourist Satisfaction on Destination Loyalty: A Conceptual Model, Vol. 11 N° 3. Special Issue. págs. 67-78. 2013, Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural, 2013
- [11] Utama, I. G., *Agrotourism as an Alternative Form of Tourism in Bali Indonesia*. Germany: Scholar Press. Retrieved 9 26, 2018, from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2517811, 2014
- [12] Utama, I. G., *Agrowisata sebagai pariwisata alternatif Indonesia: pengentasan kemiskinan secara masif*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish., 2017
- [13] Utama, I. G., *Pemasaran Pariwisata*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi, 2017
- [14] UU, N. 9. 2009., *Undang-undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 10 Tahun 2009*. Jakarta: Republik Indonesia., 2009